

ASSESSING AND COMPARING PHYSICAL ACTIVITY LEVELS OF TEACHERS AND BANKERS: A CROSS-SECTIONAL SURVEY STUDY

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Abstract

The objective of the given cross-sectional survey study was to assess and compare the physical activity level of teachers and bankers. For this purpose, samples were chosen by using convenient sampling. The IPAQ SF revised 2002 was used to collect data regarding the physical activity level among teachers and bankers. The questionnaire was filled by the teachers through hard forms and from bankers through google forms. A total number of 55 respondents share and submit their responses. The responses were analyzed by using SPSS. The descriptive statistics showed that 35% teachers had moderate physical activity level and 65% teachers had high physical activity level. 53.3% of bankers had low physical activity level and 46.7% of bankers had moderate physical activity level. Data normality tests were applied to check the normality. As the data was not normal so the non-parametric test were applied to analyze the difference between the level of physical activity of teachers and bankers. The total METs min per week were calculated. The comparison tests Mann-Whitney test and Chi-square test reports suggested that there was a statistically significant difference between the physical activity level of teachers and bankers. And teachers had statistically significant higher value of METs min per week as compared to bankers. The alternate hypothesis was accepted.

INTRODUCTION

Physical activity is associated with the health and wellbeing worldwide. If anyone regularly do any physical activity, on inculcate the physical activities in his her life, it will reduce the risk of so many diseases, mainly include cardiovascular diseases, diabetes, obesity (WHO, 2020). World health organization also claims that physical activity also enhances cognition and mental processes, muscular efficiency and overall the standard of health. But unfortunately, in spite of increasing level of physical activity, its rate continues to decline worldwide and reached the alarming level, hence increasing the rate of

diseases. According to the report of world health organization , every one fourth human being does not follow the world health organization recommended guidelines regarding physical activity, with significantly engaged in sedentary employment , with high level of inactivity. Active life style including the physically active life, is one of the best indicator to promote the healthy lifespan. Evidence based researches describes that regular physical activity lessens the occurrences of many diseases including majorly non communicable diseases like cardiovascular diseases, diabetes mainly type 2 and obesity

(WHO, 2022). Physical activity and active life style improves not only physical but also mental aspects of health include cognition and psychological wellbeing of any individual (Sharma et al, 2020).

Physical activity is no doubt important for avoiding diseases, but physical activity is not just associated with this, but it plays important role in other aspects as well. It increases many components of physical fitness like balance, muscular strength, flexibility and bones density also, which are mainly responsible of healthy aging (bull et al, 2020). Physical activity is also associated with the higher academic grades and better socialization in adults, which in turn increases the productivity and progress improvement in the workplace (guthold et al, 2023).

Universally at the level of worldwide population, due to lack of physically activity, directly increase the rate of diseases and become a cause of over 5 million deaths annually, that maybe preventable and contributing in almost 7% global rate of non-communicable diseases (katmarzyk et al, 2022). According to the recommendations of world health organization every adult individual should engage in physical activity of almost 150 to 300 minutes of moderate intensity, or vigorous or high intensity physical activity for about 75 to 150 minutes per week, and also follow the muscle strengthening activities for minimum of two days on a week. If want to get the benefits of healthy life (WHO, 2020). Hence it is clear that physical activity is not merely due to fun and enjoyment or as a leisure time activity, but it should be a health priority and part and parcel of sustainable development. The promotion of physical activity aligns with achieving the world wide settled targets, mainly includes the Sustainable development goal 3 that is related to promotion of good health and wellbeing.

It has been a great concern of measuring the physical activity levels, to pin point the high risk population or social group, so helpful in getting awareness and assessing the programs, plans and policies, and guiding how to meet the national and international r universal health targets of World health organization and Millennium

development goals (strain et al 2024, WHO, 2024).

There are many reasons for measuring the levels of physical activity. First and foremost reason to measure the level of physical activity in any social or population group let us know that how many people are following the recommended guidelines of world health organization regarding physical activity. Whether the rate of physical activity in going high or declining (WHO targets for 2030). It is essential to become aware of this rate to alarm and respond to the global trends (strain et al, 2024). The second major objective to measure the rate of physical activity of population is that, it will help the organizations to know the level of inactivity and passive life styles and make organizations aware of estimates of burden of non-communicable diseases (katmarzyk et al, 2021). Universally almost every country is striving for achieving the sustainable development goals and millennium development goals. The measurement of physical activity level helps the authorities to know and track the progress of country or specified population towards achieving the little milestones of big achievement. This indicates and evaluate that how the well countries make the environment friendly activity (WHO surveillance resources, woods et al. 2022). Another reason for measuring physical activity level is to spot out different groups who are at risk, due to little or no physical activity, can be called as high risk population group. By identifying that high risk population groups, some interventions can be designed for their welfare with reference to their health. By measuring the levels of physical activity in different groups, it was revealed that some groups show higher level of inactivity (strain et al, 2024; katzmarzyk et al, 2021).

Although the physical activity is equally important for all the individuals, in spite of the nature of their jobs, occupation etc. but it has been observed that the level of physical activity are not uniformly distributed in the society, rather differs in different social groups . Individuals associated with the sedentary nature of job more prone to inactive life style and must not involve in physical activity as due to

prolonged sitting hours required by their job. Rather the people associated with the profession of labor, are engaged in more physical activity (Ng and popkin, 2012; church et al, 2011). Similarly, people having higher economic and social status enjoy more leisure time physical activity, as compared to people of low income or low social status do not find these opportunities (beenackers et al, 2012). Gender differences also needs to be considered because it has been noted that the men involved in physical activity more as compared to women (Bauman et al, 2012). Education also effects the level of awareness of the people about their health concerns, individuals with higher education engage more in physical activities (pampel et al, 2010). Such ongoing differences highlight the need and importance of comparing the level of physical activity among different social groups. In developing countries including Pakistan, due to over population, lack of proper facilities, resource constraints, technological dependence and life style modifications further contributing in declining the level of physical activity. And very limited research have been due in this regard. Survey based assessments should be done in this regard to collect and analyze the data. Therefore the given study was conducted to assess and compare the level of physical activity of selected social groups includes teachers and bankers. The study was aimed to provide an evidence based data regarding the level of physical activity, so if needed the proper interventions and awareness programs should be organized to lessen the burden of diseases which are due to inactive life style.

Problem Statement

Physical activity is a blessing and physical inactivity is a curse and effects the lives of individuals greatly. The physical inactivity is been a major cause of global mortality, and held responsible for 3.2 million deaths per year (WHO, 2020). In Pakistan the rate of physical inactivity has been increasing and reached at an alarming level. This level of inactivity differs in different social groups. There is no or very little evidence based data available related to this.

According to a report of World health organization (WHO, 2022), more than 27.5% of individuals globally are considered as inactive, which are at high risk of non-communicable diseases. There was a great need to assess and compare the level of physical activity of different social groups. This assessment and differences are not important only academically, but also important and necessary for providing evidence based data for guiding health promotion policies and also will helpful in workplace health interventions in Pakistan.

Research Objectives

General Objective:

To assess and compare the physical activity levels of selected social groups (teachers and bankers).

Specific Objectives:

1. To measure the PA levels of teachers and bankers.
2. To compare the PA levels of teachers and bankers.

Research Question

1. What is the level of physical activity among teachers and bankers?

Hypothesis

H_{A1}: There is a significant difference in PA levels between teachers and bankers.

Methods and materials:

The researcher follows the following procedure

Research design:

A cross sectional survey research design was used in the given study to measure the level of Physical activity among teachers and bankers. The given study is a combination of descriptive and comparative research.

Population:

The population for the given research study comprised of all individuals who are teaching in different schools and who are working in banks.

Sampling:

Non-probability method of sampling i.e. convenient sampling has been used for selecting the sample.

Accessible population:

FG girls’ public school tariqabad has been selected for sample collection of teachers. The three nearest bank branches have been selected also for sample collection of bankers.

Sample size:

Total number of 45 teachers was working at the targeted school. And total 15 number of workers have been working at the given 3 bank branches. The population of interest was not too large, hence total population was taken as a sample population for the study.

Data Collection Instrument:

International physical activity questionnaire short form (IPAQ-Short form) has been used to collect the data regarding the level of physical activity among teachers and bankers. The IPAQ-SF is a validated reliable and standardized instrument which was designed specifically to assess the level of physical activity in adult’s age between 15 to 69 years across different socio economic backgrounds and associate with different domains (Craig et al, 2003). The IPAQ has been initially developed in 1998 and revised in 2002 after followed by complete validity and reliability testing across 12 different countries during 2000. Finally it has been suggested that this questionnaire has been accepted globally for measurement of physical activity across different domains. The IPAQ short form consists of only 7 close ended questions, measure the duration and frequency of physical activity from the previous seven days, with special focus on following three categories:

1. Vigorous-intensity activities for example running, heavy lifting, fast cycling.

2. Moderate-intensity activities for example brisk walking and carrying light loads.

3. Walking

The international physical activity questionnaire short form also collect the time which are spent by the participants while sitting. Then the collected responses are to be converted into metabolic equivalent task min per week, allows the researchers to analyze and categorize the data of individuals into three levels of PA: high, moderate and low. Due to its high reliability and validity this instrument is used widely worldwide (lee et al, 2011).

Data collection procedure:

Data regarding the given study was collected through hard forms (from teachers) and by a google form (bankers), international physical activity questionnaire short form. The hard form of IPAQ SF was filled by the teachers through giving them the hard forms. And the link of the questionnaire was shared with all the bankers of chosen bank branches via WhatsApp for easy access. Participants were informed about the objectives of the study and their willingness and consent was obtained before sharing the questionnaire. The participants were make sure that their responses and data will be kept confidential and their participation was completely upon their willingness. The questionnaire remained open only for the specific time and the responses were collected. The data was further analyzed by using SPSS.

Analysis of study:

The analysis of the study are given below
Descriptive statistics:

Table 1 showing the statistics of respondents of questionnaire. Total sample population was of 60 numbers. 55 respondents fill the questionnaire and 5 responses were missing.

Table 1:Table showing the Statistics of respondents of questionnaire		
physical activity level		
N	Valid	55
	Missing	5

Table 2 showing the frequency distribution of all the collected data. Total 8 (13.3%) participants had low physical activity, 21 (35%) participants had moderate physical activity level and 26(55%) respondents had high physical activity level.

Table 2: frequency distribution of physical activity level of all respondents

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Low	8	13.3	14.5	14.5
	moderate	21	35.0	38.2	52.7
	High	26	43.3	47.3	100.0
	Total	55	91.7	100.0	
Missing	System	5	8.3		
Total		60	100.0		

Physical Activity level of Teachers and Bankers:

Table 3 show the physical activity level of teachers and bankers, group wise. According to analysis report of responses of questionnaire, 35% teachers had moderate physical activity level and 65% teachers had high physical activity level. 53.3% of bankers had low physical activity level and 46.7% of bankers had moderate physical activity level.

Table 3: descriptive testing of physical activity level of teachers and bankers

			physical activity level		
			low	moderate	high
group (1= teachers, 2= bankers)	teachers	Count	0	14	26
		% within group (1= teachers, 2= bankers)	0.0%	35.0%	65.0%
		% within physical activity level	0.0%	66.7%	100.0%
	bankers	Count	8	7	0
		% within group (1= teachers, 2= bankers)	53.3%	46.7%	0.0%
		% within physical activity level	100.0%	33.3%	0.0%
Total	Count	8	21	26	
	% within group (1= teachers, 2= bankers)	14.5%	38.2%	47.3%	
	% within physical activity level	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	

Table 4: descriptive statistics of data normality

		group (1= teachers, 2= bankers)	Statistic	
total MET min per week	teachers	Mean	5328.2250	
		95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	4300.1408
			Upper Bound	6356.3092
		5% Trimmed Mean	5285.5556	
		Median	6050.0000	
		Variance	10333759.102	
		Std. Deviation	3214.61648	

		Minimum	900.00	
		Maximum	10506.00	
		Range	9606.00	
		Interquartile Range	6445.75	
		Skewness	-.178	
		Kurtosis	-1.359	
	bankers	Mean	677.4000	
		95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	462.3567
			Upper Bound	892.4433
		5% Trimmed Mean	663.7222	
		Median	556.0000	
		Variance	150790.829	
		Std. Deviation	388.31795	
		Minimum	165.00	
		Maximum	1436.00	
		Range	1271.00	
		Interquartile Range	504.00	
		Skewness	.862	
		Kurtosis	.114	

Table 5: data normality test

	group (1= teachers, 2= bankers)	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk Statistic
		Statistic	df	Sig.	
total MET min per week	Teachers	.148	40	.028	.892
	Bankers	.156	15	.200*	.915

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	group (1= teachers, 2= bankers)	Shapiro-Wilk ^a	
		df	Sig.
total MET min per week	Teachers	40	.001
	Bankers	15	.162

Table 4, 5 and 6 shows the data normality reports. Data clearly indicates that the group 1 distribution is normal but the banker’s group’s data is not normal.

Figure 1: showing the histogram of total MET min per week of teachers

Figure 2: showing the histogram of total MET min per week of bankers.

Figure 3: showing the Q-Q plot of total MET min per week of teachers.

Figure 4: showing the Q-Q plot of total MET min per week of bankers

Figure 5: showing graph to represent the total MET min per week of teachers and bankers

Inferential statistics:

Hypothesis testing:

H_{A1}: There is a significant difference in PA levels between teachers and bankers

Table 7: showing the reports of Mann-Whitney test

	group (1= teachers, 2= bankers)	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks
total MET min per week	Teachers	40	34.79	1391.50
	Bankers	15	9.90	148.50
	Total	55		

As the data was not normal so the non-parametric tests were applied to compare the means of two groups (teachers and bankers). Table 7 shows the reports of Mann-Whitney test. The result clearly indicated that there is significant differences in physical activity levels between teachers and bankers. Teachers rank was significantly higher than then the mean rank of bankers.

Table 8: Test Statistics of Mann-Whitney test

	total MET min per week
Mann-Whitney U	28.500
Wilcoxon W	148.500
Z	-5.135
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.000

Table 8 shows the P value was < 0.001 indicated that the difference between the two groups (teachers and bankers) was highly statistically significant. Teachers had a much higher mean rank than bankers. Teachers had significantly higher than the bankers.

Table 9: Case Processing Summary of Chi-Square test

				group (1= teachers, 2= Cases bankers)		Valid		Missing	
				N	Percent	N	Percent		
total MET min per week	teachers bankers			40	100.0%	0	0.0%		
	bankers			15	100.0%	0	0.0%		

Table 10: Case Processing Summary of chi-square test

		group (1= teachers, 2= bankers)		Cases Total	
		Teachers	Bankers	N	Percent
total MET min per week				40	100.0%
				15	100.0%

Table 12: chi-square group (1= teachers, 2= bankers) * physical activity level cross tabulation

			physical activity level		
			low	moderate	high
group (1= teachers, 2= bankers)	teachers	Count	0	14	26
		% within group (1= teachers, 2= bankers)	0.0%	35.0%	65.0%
		% within physical activity level	0.0%	66.7%	100.0%
		% of Total	0.0%	25.5%	47.3%
	bankers	Count	8	7	0
		% within group (1= teachers, 2= bankers)	53.3%	46.7%	0.0%
		% within physical activity level	100.0%	33.3%	0.0%
		% of Total	14.5%	12.7%	0.0%
Total	Count	8	21	26	
	% within group (1= teachers, 2= bankers)	14.5%	38.2%	47.3%	
	% within physical activity level	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	
	% of Total	14.5%	38.2%	47.3%	

Table 13: group (1= teachers, 2= bankers) * physical activity level Cross tabulation

			Total
group (1= teachers, 2= bankers)	teachers	Count	40
		% within group (1= teachers, 2= bankers)	100.0%
		% within physical activity level	72.7%
		% of Total	72.7%
	bankers	Count	15
		% within group (1= teachers, 2= bankers)	100.0%

		% within physical activity level	27.3%
		% of Total	27.3%
Total		Count	55
		% within group (1= teachers, 2= bankers)	100.0%
		% within physical activity level	100.0%
		% of Total	100.0%

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	31.472 ^a	2	.000
Likelihood Ratio	37.721	2	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	29.346	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	55		

The table 14 Pearson chi square test was conducted to check whether there is association between two categorical variables (teachers and bankers). The value of 31.472 indicated that there was strong evidence of association of the given two groups. The significant value suggested that the association was statistically significant. So the hypothesis was accepted that there is statistically significant difference between physical activity level of teachers and bankers.

Figure 6: graph showing the difference in physical activity level of teachers and bankers.

Summary:

Physical activity is an indicator of healthy life. Assessment of physical activity gives a sketch of overall health and wellbeing of society. The major objective of the given research study was to assess and compare the physical activity level of two social groups (teachers and bankers). To achieve these objectives, a survey study was conducted in the urban area of district Rawalpindi. By using convenient sampling, teaching staff of a school in district Rawalpindi was selected for participation of teachers. Three nearby bank branches were selected for participants of bankers. Total population of interest was not too large so all the participants were selected as a participant and no sampling was done. The international physical activity questionnaire short form (revised version 2002) was used to collect the data regarding the level of physical activity. The IPAQ SF was filled out by the teachers through the hard form. And a google form of IPAQ SF was designed to be filled by the bankers of all three bank staff members. A total of 55 responses were obtained and all the obtained data was analyzed through SPSS. It was observed from the reported data that, 35% teachers had moderate physical activity level and 65% teachers had high physical activity level.

53.3% of bankers had low physical activity level and 46.7% of bankers had moderate physical activity level. As the data was not normal so the non-parametric test were applied to analyze the difference between the level of physical activity of teachers and bankers. The analysis also showed that the significant value 0.00 suggested that the association Of physical activity level of teachers and bankers was statistically significant. So the hypothesis was accepted that there is statistically significant difference between physical activity level of teachers and bankers.

Conclusion

On the basis of the data findings of survey reports it was concluded that the teachers had higher MET min per week as compared to the bankers. It suggested that the teachers has a more active life style as compared to the bankers. The teaching profession involves the more movement,

from one class to another, also during classes mandatory to move in the classes. So the METs minutes per week of teachers are much higher. On the other hand the bankers have prolonged sitting hours as per requirement of the nature of their job. These findings highlights the need of workplace wellness programs for the betterment people who are working in banks and other sedentary requirement occupations or professions ,in order to make their life active rather than passive , to avoid the diseases associated with the passive lifestyle.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are hereby being proposed on the basis of findings of the given research study:

Awareness programs should be organized to make people aware of the benefits of the physical activity, whatever their occupation maybe to avoid the risk of non-communicable diseases.

Structured workplace wellness programs should be organized to promote the activity among the bankers and other employees having sedentary workplace environment. Like on workplace fitness classes, short stretching break etc.

As the bankers have prolonged sitting hours, it is recommended to incorporate standing desks to avoid the prolonged sitting and incorporate movement during the office hours.

Further studies should be conducted to make more focused and generalized results, with large number of samples.

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